

Experimental Evidence of Cohesive Force Between the CH₂ Groups of Long Chain Ions and Electrostatic Attraction Between the "Zwitter ions" of Long Chain α -Amino acids at Oil/Water Interface

B. N. Ghosh

Experimental evidence available in the literature in support of the author's view that cohesive force exists between the CH₂ groups of the neighbouring long chain ions at oil/water interface has been cited. Facts have also been recorded showing that under suitable conditions of pH, and ionic strength, long chain α -amino acids at oil/water interface exist as cations or anions and "ion pairs" of Zwitter ions. Biological significance of such equilibrium between the cations or anions and the ion pairs of Zwitter ions has been pointed out. Possibility of existence of Van der Waal's type of attraction between the "ion-pair" of the Zwitter ions and the cations or the anions of a long chain α -amino acid at the oil/water interface has been suggested.

1. *Cohesive force between the CH₂ groups of long chain ions at oil/water interface*: It is generally believed that at oil/water interface cohesive force of the Van der Waals type between the CH₂ groups of the neighbouring long chain ions does not exist. In a previous publication¹ the author has recorded some experimental data which indicate the existence of such cohesive force when the ionic head consists of N(CH₃)₃⁺ group or when the ionic strength of the aqueous solution is sufficiently low. In this paper further evidence, available in the literature in support of the author's view has been recorded.

Davies² has used the following expression to estimate the cohesive pressure π_s , at air/water interface

$$-\pi_s = (\pi_{o/w} - \pi_{a/w}) \quad \dots (1)$$

where $\pi_{o/w}$ and $\pi_{a/w}$ represent the experimentally determined values of surface pressure, for a given value of A (the area per ion), at oil/water and air/water interfaces respectively. The values of $-\pi_s$ thus estimated may be called π_s (exptl.).

He³ has also suggested the following empirical equation connecting π_s with A

$$\pi_s = \frac{400 m}{A^{3/2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where m is the effective number of CH₂ groups in the chain. In equation (2) the negative sign before π_s is dropped.

1. B. N. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 1120.
2. J. T. Davies, *J. Colloid Sc.*, 1956, **11**, 377.

Assuming Van der Waal's type of attraction between the CH_2 groups, Chatteraj and Chatterjee³ have deduced the following equation when the thickness of the interface is constant

$$\pi_s = \frac{a_s}{A^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where a_s is a constant analogous to Van der Waal's constant in two dimensions.

Using the data of Davies² for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_3^+$ at oil/water and air/water interfaces they³ have shown that for a given value of A , π_s calculated from equation (3) agrees well with that found experimentally on the basis of equation (1) so long as $A > 110(\text{\AA})^2$. When A decreases progressively below $110(\text{\AA})^2$, the difference between the values of π_s calculated from equation (3) and those observed, becomes more and more marked.

To account for this anomaly Chatteraj and Chatterjee³ have suggested that for $A > 110$ micelles of long chain ions are formed and their presence at the air/water interface necessitates correction in the value of A . On the basis of certain plausible assumptions they have deduced the following expression

$$\pi_s = \frac{a_s}{A_c^2} = \frac{a_s}{A^2} \left[1 - nx + \sqrt{\frac{a_s'}{a_s}} x \right]^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

where A_c is the corrected value of A , n represents the aggregation number, x the fraction of total molecules N_t , in associated form and a_s and a_s' are constants.

From the linear relation in equation (3) between π_s and $\frac{1}{A^2}$, for values of $A > 110$, Chatteraj and Chatterjee found the values of $a' = 90,000$ dynes/cm ($A^2/\text{molecule}$)². If the cohesive force at oil/water interface is not zero and the constant for that interface is denoted by a_0 then it follows that

$$a_s = 90,000 + a_0 \quad \dots (5)$$

Denoting the cohesive surface pressure at o/w interface by π_{so} and that at a/w interface by π_{sa} we may write

$$\pi_{so} = \frac{a_0}{A^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \pi_{sa} = \frac{90,000 + a_0}{A_c^2}$$

Since there is micellisation of the long chain ions at a/w interface only and consequently A changes to A_c at that interface, the change in the value of $\pi_{a/w}$ due to a decrease in the number of long chain ions per unit area should also be taken into account.

From theoretical consideration $\pi_{a/w}$ and $\pi_{o/w}$ may be expressed as follows :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \pi_{a/w} &= 2\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{sa} \\ \pi_{o/w} &= 2\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{so} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad \dots (6)$$

where π_k represents the pressure exerted by a long chain ion or its counter ion due to kinetic energy alone, π_r the pressure due to electrostatic repulsion and π_{sa} and π_{so} the cohesive surface pressure at air/water and oil/water interfaces respectively.

The change $\Delta\pi_k$ in surface pressure due to micelle formation by the long chain ions may be found approximately from the expression

$$\Delta\pi_k = \Delta_n kT = kT \left(\frac{1}{A} - \frac{1}{A_c} \right) \quad \dots (6b)$$

assuming the simple relation $\pi_k = nkT$ to hold good.

Therefore, for $A < 110(\text{\AA})^2$

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{o/w} - \pi_{a/w} &= (2\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{so}) - (2\pi_k - \Delta\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{sa}) \\ &= \Delta\pi_k + \pi_{sa} - \pi_{so} \\ &= \Delta\pi_k + \frac{90,000 + a_0}{A_c^2} - \frac{a_0}{A^2} \quad \dots (6c) \end{aligned}$$

In Table I are recorded the observed and calculated values of the factors involved in equation (6c) taking $a_0 = 24,000$.

It appears from the data recorded in Table I that the agreement between the values of $(\pi_{o/w} - \pi_{a/w})$ found experimentally with those calculated from equation (6c) is quite satisfactory. Hence the assumption that cohesive force exists between the CH₂ groups of the neighbouring long chain ions at *o/w* interface is justified. An idea of the magnitude of this cohesive surface pressure will be obtained from the data in column 5 of Table I.

TABLE I

Cohesive pressure of C₁₈H₃₇N(CH₃)₃⁺ monolayer

A	A _c	Δπ _k	$\frac{90,000 + a_0}{A_c^2}$	$\frac{a_0}{A^2}$	Values of (π _{o/w} - π _{a/w}) found experi- mentally		calculated from equation (6c)
90	109.1	0.79	9.58	2.96	7.3	7.4	
70	102.0	1.81	10.95	4.90	7.8	7.9	
60	96.6	2.56	12.22	6.67	8.0	8.1	
50	91.5	3.68	13.62	9.60	8.0	7.7	

Formation of dimers by long chain α-amino acids at oil/water interface : At a sufficiently low pH the molecules of a long chain α-amino acid are expected to exist mainly as cations, but as the pH is raised to approach the isoelectric point more and more "Zwitter ions" or "dual ions" are formed. It will be of considerable interest to ascertain whether they remain as monomers or form polymers at oil/water interface.

TABLE III

$\alpha = \text{amino-palmitic acid}$		
$pH=3.5$;	$A_0 = 20.5$	Ionic strength 0.1 ;
A in (\AA) ²	π observed in dynes/cm	π_c in dynes/cm calculated from equation (10)
80	3.5	3.4
110	2.4	2.2
140	1.7	1.7

monomers. The possibility of formation of a few ion pairs or dimers of the "Zwitter ions" cannot be excluded as the observed values of π are slightly smaller than the calculated values.

A comparison of the data recorded in the Tables II and III shows, that for a given value of A , the value of π at pH 3.5 is less than 1/4 of that at pH 1.7. It is, therefore, concluded that at pH 3.5 and ionic strength 0.1 the Zwitter ions of the α -amino-palmitic acid have formed dimers or 'ion-pairs' because of strong electrostatic attraction of the COO^- for the NH_3^+ group and vice versa of two neighbouring long chain ions.

Assuming that all the 'Zwitter ions' combine to form 'ion pairs' or dimers, the area available per ion pair is $2A$ and taking A_0 , the area of a CH group as 20.5 (\AA)², the value for two such groups in the 'ion-pair' should be $2A_0$. The ion-pair or the dimer will behave as a neutral molecule and so its pressure, π , at oil/water interface should follow equation (10).

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table III that the observed values of π_c agree well with those calculated from equation (10). It may, therefore, be concluded that at pH 3.5 and ionic strength 0.1, only 'ion-pair' or dimers of α -amino-palmitic acid exists at oil/water interface.

It may be mentioned that on the basis of Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium, even at a constant pH of the aqueous solution, the proportion of 'ion-pairs' or dimers of Zwitter ions formed at the oil/water interface should depend on the ionic strength of the solution. Thus at a constant pH , increase in the concentration of a salt like NaCl will increase at the oil/water interface the proportion of the cations or the anions at the expense of 'ion-pairs'. The possibility of such polymerisation of α -amino acids at the interface of cell wall/cell fluid is worth-noting.

It may also be pointed out that under conditions in which the monomer ions and the 'ion-pair' of 'Zwitter ions' are both present at the oil/water interface, the close proximity of a monomer ion to an 'ion-pair' may enhance, by induction, the dipole character of the 'ion-pair' and thereby give rise to attraction of the Van der Waal's type.

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